

LINGUO-COGNITIVE MODELING OF DERIVATIVE WORD SEMANTICS FORMED FROM PRECEDENT NAMES (BASED ON THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE)

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Abstract: this article explores the linguo-cognitive mechanisms involved in the formation and semantic modeling of derivative words from precedent names in the English language. It focuses on how cognitive tools such as metaphor and metonymy facilitate the extension of cultural meaning from these names, resulting in concise linguistic expressions that reflect collective cultural memory and contextual variability.

Keywords: precedent names, derivative words, cognitive linguistics, metaphor, metonymy, cultural memory.

The study of derivative words formed from precedent names in the English language is a rich area of linguistic research that intersects cognitive linguistics and cultural studies. Precedent names—names of people, places, events, or characters that carry significant cultural weight—serve as sources for creating derivative words with new meanings. These names, often derived from literature, history, mythology, and popular culture, provide a powerful cognitive framework for forming new linguistic expressions that reflect collective cultural memory.

Precedent names, sometimes referred to as iconic or culturally significant names, carry meanings beyond their literal reference. They act as cognitive triggers that activate complex associations related to their source. For example, when someone is called a "Hercules," the reference is not to the mythological figure directly, but to the qualities of strength and heroism that Hercules symbolizes in Western culture.

These names serve multiple functions in communication:

1. Summarization of complex ideas: A single name like "Einstein" can convey intelligence, genius, or scientific brilliance.
2. Cultural references: Precedent names often encapsulate shared knowledge or collective memories, such as "Napoleonic" referring to someone ambitious, perhaps overreaching.
3. Moral and evaluative judgments: Names like "Judas" are used metaphorically to judge someone as a traitor.

The creation of derivative words from precedent names involves several cognitive mechanisms, including metaphor, metonymy, analogy, and association.

These mechanisms allow for the transfer of cultural meaning from the original name to a broader range of contexts, establishing new semantic fields.

1. **Metaphor:** One of the key cognitive mechanisms in the creation of derivatives is metaphor. Through metaphor, characteristics associated with the original name are mapped onto new domains. For example, "Herculean" tasks are those that require immense effort or strength, metaphorically borrowing from the image of Hercules. Example: "It was a Herculean effort to complete the project on time." In this sentence, "Herculean" conveys the idea of extraordinary strength or perseverance, metaphorically extending the qualities of the mythological figure to a challenging task.

2. **Metonymy:** Metonymy involves the substitution of one concept with another that is closely related. In the case of precedent names, metonymy often shifts focus from a specific historical or fictional figure to a broader, more generalized concept. Example: "She's a real Shakespeare in the making." Here, "Shakespeare" metonymically represents not the historical playwright himself but the qualities associated with him—literary talent, creativity, and excellence in writing.

3. **Analogy and association:** Precedent names often generate derivatives through analogical extension, where the name becomes a prototype for a set of features that are then applied in new contexts. This process relies heavily on cultural and cognitive associations that the name triggers. Example: "His behavior was Orwellian." "Orwellian" is derived from the name George Orwell, whose works like "1984" have come to symbolize totalitarianism, oppressive surveillance, and manipulation of truth.

The linguo-cognitive modeling of derivative words formed from precedent names in the English language reveals the complex interplay between language, culture, and cognition. These derivative words serve as linguistic tools that condense rich cultural meanings into concise expressions. Through mechanisms like metaphor, metonymy, and analogy, precedent names extend their semantic reach and continue to shape the way we communicate.

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